

Coordination Complexes of Chlorophenoxy Derivatives of Titanium(IV) with α -Hydroxy Aldehydes and Ketones

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Monochloro-, dichloro- and trichloro-titanium(IV) chlorophenoxides react with benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde in appropriate molar ratio to form compounds of composition $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_3 \cdot L$; $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl)_2 \cdot L$ and $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_2 \cdot 2L$; and $TiCl_2(OC_6H_4Cl) \cdot L$ and $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl) \cdot 2L$, respectively. Based on elemental analysis, conductance, cryoscopic and infrared spectral studies, their possible structures have been elucidated.

MEHROTRA *et al.*¹ investigated the reactions of alkoxides of titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) with salicylaldehyde. Benzoin and substituted-benzoin form stable chelates with halides of titanium(IV)². α -Hydroxycarboxylic acids and salicylic acids also react with alkoxides of these metals^{3,4}. Gopinathan *et al.*⁵ reported salicylaldehyde-oxotitanium monoalkoxide. In our earlier communication⁶, we reported the synthesis of chlorophenoxy derivatives of titanium(IV). We now report their reactivity towards protons of α -hydroxy aldehydes and ketones.

Experimental

Chlorophenoxy derivatives of titanium(IV) of composition $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_4$, $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl)_3$, $TiCl_2(OC_6H_4Cl)_2$ and $TiCl_3(OC_6H_4Cl)$ were prepared by the methods reported earlier⁶. Benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde were purified by crystallisation or distillation before use.

Compounds of composition $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_3 \cdot L$; $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl)_2 \cdot L$ and $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_2 \cdot 2L$; and $TiCl_2(OC_6H_4Cl) \cdot L$ and $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl) \cdot 2L$ were prepared by refluxing the ligands, such as benzoin (benzH), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapH) or salicylaldehyde (salH) with monochloro-, dichloro- or trichloro-titanium(IV) chlorophenoxides in benzene in predetermined molar ratios till there was no evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. The compounds were isolated as solids either by the addition of petroleum ether to the resulting solutions or on cooling. The solid compounds were filtered, washed and dried under reduced pressure.

Titanium was estimated as titanium dioxide and chlorine by Volhard's method. Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solution of the compounds in $PhNO_2$ were measured on a Elico conductivity bridge using a cell having cell constant 0.334 at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Infrared spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer double grating spectrophotometer. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically by Beckmann method.

Results and Discussion

The compounds which have been isolated in the present studies are listed in Table 1. Stoichiometric composition of the compounds has been established by elemental analysis. Possible reactions showing the formation of resulting compounds may be

where, L is anion of benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone or salicylaldehyde. Similar reactions may be proposed in case of other chlorophenoxide complexes. All the compounds are highly moisture-sensitive solids and change their colours in air. The compounds are fairly soluble in benzene, nitrobenzene and acetonitrile. Molar conductance values of their millimolar solutions in nitrobenzene suggest them to be non-electrolytes⁷. Molecular weights of some of these compounds determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene suggest that compounds of composition $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_2 \cdot 2L$ and $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl) \cdot 2L$ are monomers while the compounds of composition $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_3 \cdot L$, $TiCl_2(OC_6H_4Cl) \cdot L$ and $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl) \cdot L$ are dimers.

Intramolecular hydrogen bonding in α -hydroxy aldehydes and ketones causes ν_{OH} generally observed at $3500-3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in alcohols and phenols to shift to lower regions at 3390 , 3410 and 3180 cm^{-1} in pure benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde, respectively^{8,9}. These bands are absent in the spectra of their complexes with chlorophenoxy derivatives of titanium(IV), suggest deprotonation of phenolic OH, an observation which is also supported by the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas during the course of reaction. Coordination of oxygen of the hydroxyl group is confirmed by the lowering of $\nu_{C=O}$ from $1090-1110$ to $1035-1050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. A sharp and strong band at $1640-1680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands assigned^{8,9} to $\nu_{C=O}$

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)*		Molar conductance** Ω cm ² mol ⁻¹	Mol. weight** Found/(Calcd.)	ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)		
			Ti	Cl			O=O	Ti-O	Ti-Cl
benzH	White	—	—	—	—	—	9 370 ^b 1 670	—	—
Ti(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .benz	Blackish brown	75	7.71 (7.48)	16.90 (16.60)	1.76	1258 (641.7)	1 596	598, 512	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .benz	Light brown	212 ^a	9.11 (8.73)	18.56 (18.39)	2.08	1089 (549.7)	1 602	595, 510	362
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).benz	Light brown	184	10.27 (10.49)	23.01 (23.26)	3.01	910 (457.7)	1 608	600, 508	368
Ti(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2benz	Dark brown	188 ^a	6.32 (6.61)	10.03 (9.79)	1.97	708 (725.5)	1 601	592	—
hapH	Colourless	—	—	—	—	—	3 410 ^b 1 640	—	—
Ti(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .hap	Red	55	8.34 (8.49)	18.64 (18.83)	3.24	— (565.5)	1 582	595, 504	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .hap	Yellow	70	9.97 (10.11)	22.13 (22.44)	2.76	— (478.5)	1 580	596, 509	368
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).hap	Maroon	60	12.94 (12.58)	27.74 (27.91)	1.64	749 (381.5)	1 575	595, 502	362
Ti(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2hap	Brick red	56	8.71 (8.38)	12.51 (12.39)	2.49	558 (573)	1 578	600	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2hap	Reddish	80	9.87 (10.02)	14.42 (14.76)	1.90	468 (481)	1 582	598	362
salH	Colourless	—	—	—	—	—	3 180 ^b 1 660	—	—
Ti(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .sal	Reddish	250 ^a	9.01 (8.70)	19.77 (19.31)	3.44	1097 (551.6)	1 592	590, 510	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .sal	Reddish	325 ^a	10.74 (10.45)	23.53 (23.17)	2.16	— (459.6)	1 595	590, 515	366
TiCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).sal	Brick red	208 ^a	13.20 (13.06)	29.23 (28.97)	1.34	— (367.6)	1 590	595, 506	366
Ti(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl) ₂ .2sal	Reddish	116 ^a	9.07 (8.81)	13.71 (13.02)	2.52	539 (545.2)	1 598	602	—
TiCl(OC ₆ H ₄ Cl).2sal	Maroon	210 ^a	10.13 (10.59)	16.05 (15.67)	2.36	440 (453.2)	1 602	598	364

* C and H analyses found satisfactory. **In nitrobenzene.

^aDecomp. temp. ^bν_{OH}.

is lowered by 60–70 cm⁻¹ on complexation, thereby indicating the coordination from the oxygen of the carbonyl group as well to titanium. Apart from these bands, ν_{C=C} modes present around 1 200 cm⁻¹ in the pure ligands have been found to shift to higher spectral regions in their complexes. Similar observations have also been made earlier^{10,11}.

Low frequency ir spectrum of these compounds has been very helpful to elucidate their structures. In case of compounds of composition TiCl(OC₆H₄Cl)₂.2L and Ti(OC₆H₄Cl)₂.2L, the bands present at 508–520 cm⁻¹ in the parent chlorophen-

oxides⁶ due to bridging Ti modes are absent in the complexes. In stead sharp bands at 590–600 cm⁻¹ have been observed which may be assigned to terminal Ti–O stretching modes. The absence

of bridging Ti modes in these compounds suggests that a breakdown of chlorophenoxy bridges followed by coordination of the ligand to the central metal help the metal to acquire its favoured coordination number of six in an octahedral environment and is in agreement with the earlier reports¹².

Contrary to the above observations, ir spectra of the compounds of composition Ti(OC₆H₄Cl)₂.L, TiCl(OC₆H₄Cl)₂.L and TiCl₂(OC₆H₄Cl).L, exhibit

bands due to both bridging Ti Ti and terminal Ti–O stretching modes, thus suggesting the retention of chlorophenoxy bridges even on complexation with the hydroxy ketones which is also supported by molecular weights. Sharp intense bands observed at 350–360 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to terminal Ti–Cl stretching modes in an octahedral environment^{6,12}. The band that could be assigned

to bridging Ti Ti expected to fall well below 300 cm⁻¹ has not been observed, which excludes the possibility of bridging through chlorine atoms in these compounds. It is important to mention here that there is no splitting of bands due to ν_{Ti-Cl} and the spectra of the compounds like TiCl₂(OC₆H₄Cl).L are simple which thereby excludes the possibility of *cis*-positions for the chlorine atoms. Thus based on elemental analysis, conductance, molecular weight and ir spectral studies, a possible dimeric structure having chloro

phenoxy bridge may be proposed for the compound $TiCl_2(OC_6H_4Cl)_2.L$ as

Similar structures may be proposed for the compounds $Ti(OC_6H_4Cl)_3.L$ and $TiCl(OC_6H_4Cl)_2.L$.

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